

Mapping with older adults: how do older adults' ratings of streets compare to researcher led audits

Dr Angela Curl

angela.curl@otago.ac.nz

University
of Otago

ŌTĀKOU WHAKAIHU WAKA

Ōtautahi
Christchurch
Campus

Outdoor mobility and wellbeing

- **Mobility → wellbeing** (Schwanen & Ziegler, 2011; Gattrell, 2013)
 - Facilitator
 - Physical/mental health
 - Motility – potential to move
- Walking an important mode of transport and source of physical activity for older adults
- Walking ~ falls risk, cardio-vascular health, obesity, diabetes, mood, social connection.....
- Risk of falls and fear of falling associated with reduced mobility and outdoor walking

Why outdoor falls?

- Most falls among over 60s happen **at home (71%)** * ACC 10 year data 2013-2023
- 6% occur on the **road or street*** ACC 10 year data 2013-2023
- BUT *Falling and fear of falling* restrict outdoor mobility and affect physical and mental wellbeing and accessibility
- AND first, less injurious falls outside - then restrict outdoor mobility

Google

© 2017 Google Terms of Use Report a problem

Type an address, neighborhood or city

26 Bealey Avenue

[Add scores to your site](#)

-
-
-

Walk Score
79

Very Walkable

Most errands can be accomplished on foot.

About your score

Aims

1. Use a participatory approach to audit the built environment for pedestrian falls risks
2. Examine differences in researcher led assessments and assessments undertaken by community members
3. Examine whether specific demographic characteristics can account for differences in assessment of locations between participants

Fall location data

Created by Atif Arshad
from Noun Project

- July 2016-June 2018
- 7,416 falls on the road or street (6%)
- 3,519 among those aged over 60 (54%)
- 2,530 in urban areas

Virtual audits using Google Street View (researcher led)

Most locations had a footpath on both sides (88%) and a crossing (77%).

Many sites (43%) were near a shop or commercial property with a street facing entrance, and had a visible public seat (34%).

Asphalt (40%) and concrete (45%) paths were most common, but paving bricks were common in 'high street' locations (65% of this location type).

Almost all sites had streetlights, but 55% had lights only on one side.

Community engagement process

Recruited participants into workshops through local contacts and community organisations

Workshop format:

-Brief overview of research and context of outdoor falls

-Complete consent forms and participant information questionnaire (demographics +)

-Open discussion – recorded

-Completed audits using iPads – drop and spin

37 participants across 12 workshops

Three quarters female

Average age 69 (32-92)

222 unique locations assessed

592 records – 222 researcher site assessments and 370 community assessments

(dis)agreement among participants

Item	% agreement
Attractiveness	32.6
Difficulty walking	23
Concern for falling	37.9
Slope	67
Trip hazards	27.6
Obstructions	
<i>Poles</i>	57.3
<i>Signs</i>	68.5
<i>Bins</i>	83.1
<i>Overgrowth</i>	100
<i>Planters</i>	100
<i>Manholes</i>	64
<i>Utility boxes</i>	100

Dr Alison
Watkins

Tessa Pocock

Cushla Dares

Dr Verity Todd

Dr Bridget
Dicker

Dr Jonathan
Williman

Amanda
Smithies

Dr Sally Keeling

St John
Here for Life

Michelle Brett

**Thanks to:
Age Concern
Waimakariri District Council
ACTIS
Aranui Library
All our participants**

Thank you

angela.curl@otago.ac.nz